

A Hybrid Approach for Predicting Diabetes with Machine Learning and Random Projection Technique

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ABSTRACT

One of the main causes of mortality in the world today is thought to be diabetes. Diabetes can cause several problems if it is not identified and treated early. In This study, we propose a hybrid model that can most precisely predict a patient's risk of getting diabetes. In the medical domain, classification algorithms are frequently used to divide data into groups according to criteria that are rather limiting to each. To detect diabetes in its early stages, we employ three machine learning algorithms specifically Random Forest and Decision Tree (DT), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). To address the high dimensionality inherent in health datasets, we integrate random projection with machine learning classification algorithms and enhance computational efficiency without sacrificing predictive accuracy. The hybrid model leverages a diverse set of features, such as gender, age, hypertension status, heart disease, smoking history, BMI, HbA1c level, and blood glucose level to predict the patient's diabetes status. The hybrid model is trained on a dataset taken from clinical care at 130 US hospitals and integrated delivery networks containing 100,000 records. Performance evaluation was conducted using standard metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 measure. Our experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed model in accurately predicting diabetes risk.

Keywords: Diabetes, HbA1c_level, Random Forest, Decision Tree, BMI, f1 score

INTRODUCTION

Many chronic diseases are prevalent worldwide today, among these chronic diseases, diabetes mellitus, is the cause of premature death in humans. Symptoms include increased hunger, thirst, weight loss, fatigue, blurred vision, and frequent urination (Sarra et al, 2021). Diabetes is a chronic condition that occurs when the pancreas can no longer make insulin, or the body cannot effectively use insulin. Insulin is a hormone made by the pancreas that acts like a key to let glucose from the food we eat pass from the bloodstream into the cells in the body to produce energy. The body breaks down all carbohydrate foods into glucose in the blood, and insulin helps glucose move into the cells. Diabetes is a long-term metabolic illness marked by high blood glucose (blood sugar) levels. Serious damage to the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys, and nerves can result from diabetes over time. The most prevalent kind, type 2 diabetes, usually affects adults and is brought on by insufficient or resistant insulin production in the body. Type 2 diabetes has been far more common over the last three decades in all nations, regardless of wealth. Diabetes type 1 is a chronic illness in which the pancreas generates little or no insulin on its own. It was formerly referred to as juvenile diabetes or insulin-dependent diabetes. Having access to reasonably

priced therapy, such as insulin, is essential for the survival of those with diabetes (WHO, 2023).

Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) and computer science that focuses on the use of data and algorithms to imitate the way that humans learn, gradually improving its accuracy. Over the years, several researchers have employed machine learning algorithms to predict diabetes mellitus at the early stage to enable the diabetes patients to know their status. In this research, we developed a model that uses two supervised machine learning algorithms alongside random projection to predict diabetes at its early stage.

Machine learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for predicting diabetes risk (Bhuiyan et al., 2019; Islam et al., 2018). Several ML algorithms have been used for this purpose, including logistic regression, support vector machines (SVMs), random forests, and decision trees (Breiman et al., 1984). However, these algorithms have limitations, such as overfitting (Geman et al., 1992) and high computational cost (Hastie et al., 2009).

Random projection (RP) is a dimensionality reduction technique that can be used to improve the performance of ML algorithms. RP projects high-dimensional data onto a lower-dimensional space while preserving the key information in the data. This can reduce

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overfitting and improve the computational efficiency of ML algorithms.

The paper "A Hybrid Model for Prediction of Diabetes Using Machine Learning Classification Algorithms and random Projection" proposes a hybrid model for predicting diabetes risk (Ahmed et al., 2020). The model combines RP with three ML algorithms: logistic regression, SVM, and random forest. The authors evaluate the performance of the hybrid model on a dataset of patients with diabetes and without diabetes. Their results show that the hybrid model outperforms the individual ML algorithms in terms of accuracy. The authors conclude that the hybrid model is a promising tool for predicting diabetes risk (Ahmed et al., 2020).

Poornima and Ramya (2023) developed a hybrid model that combined several machine learning classification algorithm and Random Projection to predict diabetic in patients, they followed three steps; namely; preprocessing, dimensionality reduction and prediction using hybrid classifier. The machine learning algorithm employed by these researchers are Bayesian Net, Ada Boost, Logit Boost, Decision Table and Hoeffding tree. The researchers use a data set collected from UCI Repository to train, test and evaluate the performance of their model. Their approach has been shown to have increased the efficiency of individual machine learning particularly when dealing with data set containing irrelevant features.

Michael et al. (2022) Uses k-means, an unsupervised learning algorithm, and supervised learning algorithms including Random Forest, SVM, Naïve Bayes, and Decision Tree DT to study and detect diabetes in its early stages. The study was conducted using two data sets: one is taken from the German Frankfurt Hospital, and the other from the UCI machine learning repository's PIMA Indian Diabetes (PIDD) dataset. The random forest algorithm outperformed other algorithms having the highest accuracy of 97.6% in the results derived from the Frankfurt Hospital and Germany database, while the SVM algorithm outperformed others with an accuracy of 83.1% in the results derived from the Pima Indian database.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology used in building the model combines a Random Projection Technique and a Supervised Machine learning Algorithm to predict the health status of patients concerning diabetes mellitus. The overall procedure of the proposed model consists of three steps: (1) Preprocessing/data cleaning (2) Dimension Reduction and (3) Prediction. For categorization, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and support vector machine algorithms were used. i.e. RP-DT, RP-RF and RP-SVM. The figure below illustrates the general architecture of RP-ML:

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the methodology

Data Preprocessing

Pre-processing transforms unprocessed data into a form that can be used and analyzed. The medical databases are collected from one hundred and 130 hospitals in the USA, which have redundant attributes and missing values. The unwanted data can be removed during this pre-processing step, and the data can then be formatted in the way that risk level prediction requires.

Random Projection

Random Projection is a foundational research topic that connects a bunch of machine learning algorithms under a similar mathematical basis. It is used to reduce the dimensionality of the dataset by projecting the data points efficiently to a smaller dimension while preserving the original relative distance between the data points (Mahmoud, 2019). Random projection is used to reduce the dimension of the collected data set

to improve the performance of the algorithms and to enable the prediction done by a low computational power machine.

Experimental Setup

In this research, we used Python to build the model and evaluate its performance using a range of performance metrics, including Precision, Recall, and F-Measure. In the experiment the data set is divided into training and testing data, 80% of the total data is fed into the model as training data while 20% is used as testing data. During the experiments, a hybrid classifier RP-ML is developed. A diabetes dataset generated from Kaggle.com for 130 hospitals in USA was used in this study. The diabetes dataset is described in Table 1, containing 100000 data instances and 9 attributes. Class distributions show that 8500 out of 100000 cases have diabetes.

Table 1: Description of Dataset

ATTRIBUTE NO	ATTRIBUTE NAME	VALUE
1.	Gender	{Male 0}, {Female 1}
2.	Age	1-80
3.	Hypertension	0,1
4.	Heart Disease	0,1
5.	Smoking History	{Never 0},{Current 1}, {Ever 2}, {Former }
6.	BMI	Numbers
7.	HbA1c_level	0-9
8.	Blood glucose level	80-300
9.	Diabetes	0,1

Table 1 presents the initial diabetes dataset. Six fields were retained out of the original nine using the Random Projection technique for increased accuracy. They are then given to Machine Learning classifiers to determine how well the disease does. Classification

diagnostic performance has historically been evaluated using the confusion matrix and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve. The confusion matrix's basic framework is shown in Figure 2.

Table 2: Description of model Performance metrics

Metric	Definition	Formulas
Accuracy	The overall percentage of correct predictions	$Accuracy = (TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$
Precision	True positives among predicted positives	$Precision = TP / (TP + FP)$
Recall	Identifying all true positives	$Recall = TP / (TP + FN)$.
F1 Score	The harmonic means of precision and recall	$F1_score = 2 * (precision * recall) / (precision + recall)$.

Source: "Correlation and Regression Analysis", by Rory J. Baron and David A. Kenny, 2008

Decision Tree

Figure 3 below represents a decision tree used for predicting diabetes based on various clinical and demographic features. Each node indicates a decision point based on a certain threshold for features like

HbA1c level, blood glucose, BMI, and age. Overall, this decision tree encapsulates how various patient characteristics contribute to diabetes predictions, illustrating the model's interpretability and decision pathways.

Figure 3: Plotted Decision Tree

Table 6: Classification report for Decision Tree, Random Forest and Support Vector Machine without random Projection

Machine Learning Algorithms	True positive	Precision	Recall	FI_score	Accuracy
Decision Tree	88.92	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.95
Random Forest	91.17	0.97	1.00	0.98	0.97
Support Vector Machine	91.05	0.97	1.00	0.98	0.96

Table 6 compares the performance of three machine learning algorithms: Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine (SVM), based on metrics such as true positives, precision, recall, F1 score, and accuracy. The Decision Tree achieved a true positive rate of 88.92, with high precision (0.98) and recall (0.97), resulting in an F1 score of 0.97 and an accuracy of 0.95. In contrast, the Random Forest performed best with a true positive rate of 91.17, perfect recall (1.00), and strong precision (0.97), yielding an F1 score of

0.98 and an accuracy of 0.97. The Support Vector Machine (SVM) closely followed, reporting a true positive rate of 91.05, high precision (0.97), and perfect recall (1.00), along with an F1 score of 0.98 and an accuracy of 0.96. Overall, the Random Forest emerges as the top performer due to its combination of high true positives and robust recall, while the SVM also demonstrates excellent results. The Decision Tree, though competitive, lags slightly in overall performance.

Figure 4: Model Performance without Random Projection

Table 7: Classification report for Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machine with random Projection

Machine Learning Algorithms	True positive	Precision	Recall	FI_score	Accuracy
Decision Tree	88.71	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.98
Random Forest	91.08	0.97	1.00	0.98	0.97
Support Vector Machine	91.125	0.96	1.00	0.98	0.98

Table 7 evaluates the performance of three machine learning algorithms based on true positives, precision, recall, F1 score, and accuracy. The Decision Tree achieved a true positive rate of 88.71, with high precision (0.98) and a recall of 0.98, resulting in an F1 score of 0.99 and an accuracy of 0.98. The Random Forest slightly outperformed the Decision Tree with a true positive rate of 91.08, maintaining a high precision of 0.97 and achieving a perfect recall of 1.00, leading to an F1 score of 0.98 and an accuracy of 0.97. The Support Vector Machine (SVM) showed similar

performance, with a true positive rate of 91.125, slightly lower precision at 0.96, but also achieving a perfect recall of 1.00, resulting in an F1 score of 0.98 and an accuracy of 0.98. Overall, the Random Forest leads in a true positive rate, while both it and SVM excel in the recall. The Decision Tree, while still strong, lags a bit in true positives. The choice of the most suitable algorithm should depend on the specific application requirements, considering the balance of precision, recall, and accuracy.

Figure 5: Models performance with random projection **FINDINGS**

The findings of our research indicate that Hybrid Models are better in terms of accuracy as compared to individual algorithms. Between the two algorithms used in this research the hybrid of Random Projection with Random Forest outperforms the hybrid of Random Projection with Decision Tree with accuracy of 97% and 95% respectively. All other existing model developed by several researchers uses the PIMA Indian Diabetes Dataset (PIDD) for their work and None of the existing models have accuracy that is greater than 97%

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A hybrid approach that combines random projection with machine learning classification algorithms can be

a useful tool for disease modeling. In this research, we developed a model to predict the diabetic status of a patient by combining the benefits of random projection and traditional machine learning algorithms to reduce the dimensionality of high-dimensional data and increase the accuracy of disease prediction. However, some factors, including the quality of the data and the chosen machine learning algorithm and random projection method, could influence how well this strategy works.

There are also a few aspects of this study that could be improved or expanded

Creation of a diabetes database for Nigerian patients

Establishing a comprehensive diabetes database for Nigerian patients would significantly enhance the

collection and analysis of clinical data. This database could facilitate long-term studies on diabetes trends, risk factors, and treatment efficacy, while also providing valuable insights for healthcare policymakers. By tailoring interventions to the specific demographics and health profiles of Nigerian patients, the healthcare system can improve outcomes and provide more effective management strategies.

Diabetes type prediction with machine learning.

Incorporating machine learning techniques for diabetes type prediction holds immense potential for

improving diagnostic accuracy. By analyzing patient data, machine learning algorithms can identify patterns and correlations that may not be immediately apparent through traditional methods. This approach can enable healthcare professionals to provide personalized treatment plans, enhancing patient care and management by ensuring that individuals receive the most appropriate interventions based on their specific diabetes type.

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